

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Special track

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Spatti, A. C., Bin, A., Salles-Filho, S. M., de Lima Sgobi, B., & Mena-Chalco, J. (2022). Does funding affect gendered scientific impact in an emerging economy?. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22110). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6951524>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Does funding affect gendered scientific impact in an emerging economy?¹

Ana Carolina Spatti*, Adriana Bin*, Sérgio Monteiro Salles-Filho**, Beatriz de Lima Sgobi* and Jesus Mena-Chalco***

* *anaspatti@ige.unicamp.br; adribin@unicamp.br; beatrizsgobi127@gmail.com*

University of Campinas, School of Applied Sciences (Brazil), Pedro Zaccaria Street, 1300, Limeira – SP

** *sallesfi@unicamp.br*

University of Campinas, Institute of Geosciences (Brazil), Rua Carlos Gomes, 250, Campinas – SP

*** *jjesus.mena@ufabc.edu.br*

Federal University of ABC, Center for Mathematics, Computation and Cognition (Brazil), Av. dos Estados, 5001, Santo André – SP

Introduction

Despite long-standing discussions about the representation of women in academia, gender inequalities persist. The literature provides evidence that women publish less than men (Addressi et al. 2012), are less cited (Bellotti et al., 2022), are scarcer in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) disciplines (Lincoln et al., 2012) and less represented in academic higher grades (Sugimoto, 2018).

In this article, we are interested in the relationship between funding and scientific impact from a gender perspective. On the one hand, access to research funding is an important mechanism for the success of academic careers for men and women and for the development of the research system. On the other hand, funding can be a mechanism that strengthens gender inequality in academia. Other studies have shown interest in the evaluation system and the peer review process of grants, but do not address the scientific performance of fellows after they have received funding. Therefore, we wish to know if funding affects gendered scientific impact. Specifically, we are interested in empirically evaluate the performance of young researchers who have received a research grant from one of the largest funding agencies in Brazil, FAPESP (São Paulo Research Foundation), to identify whether scientific production between men and women differ.

Background

Women are the majority in Brazilian universities. In 2015, postgraduate courses had 11,000

¹ This work was supported by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP), Award Number 2017/17461-1 and 2021/00508-0.

more women enrolled than men. In the SciELO database (the most relevant Latin American scientific repository), publications by female authors represented 32.28% of outputs in 2006, with the strongest concentration in Human Sciences and Linguistics, Languages and Arts and the lowest in Engineering.

The São Paulo Research Foundation – FAPESP

Brazil's research funding system for Ph.D. students is organized at federal and state levels. At the federal level, scholarships are awarded by the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) and the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq). State research funding agencies also award scholarships, and FAPESP is the largest. It uses a classical peer-reviewed process for awarding grants. Criteria involve student's academic performance, supervisor's experience and expertise, and project quality. Ph.D. students from the state of São Paulo can apply for a scholarship under institutional quota (CNPq or CAPES) or directly to FAPESP.

Brazil's research funding system for Ph.D. students is organized at federal and state levels. At the federal level, scholarships are awarded by the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) and the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq). State research funding agencies also award scholarships, and FAPESP is the largest. It uses a classical peer-reviewed process for awarding grants. Criteria involve student's academic performance, supervisor's experience and expertise, and project quality. Ph.D. students from the state of São Paulo can apply for a scholarship under institutional quota (CNPq or CAPES) or directly to FAPESP.

Data and Methodology

In this research, we wish to employ a quasi-experimental approach with ex post facto design. So far, we haven't modelled our data to measure the "FAPESP scholarship effect". However, we will highlight some findings from the descriptive analysis of our data and present our research groups which will be latter used for the quasi-experiment.

Our study population is composed of all the individuals who applied for FAPESP's doctoral scholarships between 2003 and 2017 and have concluded their Ph.D. degree (all information provided by FAPESP). The first group, named "FAPESP awardees", refers to those who were granted a scholarship by this institution. Within the design of our quasi-experiment, this is considered our treatment group. The second group, "Other awardees", refers to rejected candidates who, nonetheless, were granted a scholarship from other institutions. Finally, the third group, "No awardees", encompasses all those rejected who completed their Ph.D. without any funding. These last two are our control groups. Table 1 shows the number of individuals in each group.

Table 1. *Eligible population for each quasi-experiment*

Quasi-experiment	Treatment Group (FAPESP Awardees)	Control Group 1 (Other Awardees)	Control Group 2 (No Awardees)	Total
Female	7,040	3,951	913	11,904 (56,8%)
Male	5,545	2,829	691	9,065 (43,2%)
Total	12,585	6,780	1,604	20,969 (100%)

From the CAPES and FAPESP databases and the Lattes *Curriculum Vitae* (Lattes – a national platform for registered academic curricula), we retrieved information about timing of previous academic stages (Bs.C and MS.c), Ph.D. period, knowledge field of doctoral research, enrolled post-graduation program, host institution, geographic location, and financial support. We highlight that Lattes is considered a rich and powerful database for scientific and technological information about students, professors, researchers, and professionals involved in science and technology fields in Brazil.

Data related to scholarly publications was systematically collected using Lattes in April 2019. Scholarly publications were organized in four categories: (i) papers published in journals; (ii) papers in conference proceedings; (iii) books; and (iv) book chapters.

We assigned gender information to the authors (male or female) based on the data retrieved from Lattes. Identification was done in two ways: (i) using the information provided by the researcher; (ii) applying a gender identification program to the first name in the cases in which gender was not pre-specified in the curriculum.

Preliminary Results and Discussion

In this section, we present the descriptive statistics of our population’s scholarly production after Ph.D. conclusion according to the four aforementioned categories, namely the number of published papers in scientific journals (Figure 1), in conferences (Figure 2), published books (Figure 3) and book chapters (Figure 4). All values refer to the mean for each gender and assessment group. Furthermore, to better visualize differences, we’ve segmented these results according to fields of research: Agricultural Sciences (AGR), Biological Sciences (BIO), Health Sciences (HEA), Exact and Earth Sciences (EXER), Human Sciences (HUM), Social Applied Sciences (SOC), Engineering (ENG), Interdisciplinary (INT), and Linguistics, Literature, and Arts (LLA).

Figure 1. Scholarly output (mean per author) by gender, group and field– journal paper

Figure 2. Scholarly output (mean per author) by gender, group and field – conference papers

Figure 3. Scholarly output (mean per author) by gender, group and field – books

Figure 4. Scholarly output (mean per author) by gender, group and field – book chapters

Preliminary Remarks

In general terms, FAPESP awardees have the highest mean number of publications in almost all fields of research. Nonetheless, the other groups of analysis (Other awardees and No awardees) perform relatively better in some specific sets.

Within the “journal papers” category, female FAPESP awardees are less productive in EXER, INT and SOC fields when compared to female in control groups. For men, this occurs in HUM and INT. In the “conference papers” category, we can see that FAPESP awardees, both men and women, publish less in HUM, INT, LLA and EXER in comparison to control groups. FAPESP female awardees also publish less in SOC while FAPESP male awardees publish less in AGR.

As for “published books”, female no awardees perform better than control groups in ENG, EXER, INT and SOC and the male no awardees in ENG, EXER, HUM and SOC. Finally, in the “book chapter” category, female FAPESP awardees are less productive than control groups in ENG, EXER, HEA, INT and SOC and male in AGR, EXER, HUM and LLA. In general, FAPESP awardees perform better in most common used venues for each knowledge field.

When considering journal articles as the academic output of analysis, women seem to underperform in all fields of research compared to men. However, we cannot generalize these results to every scientific product or fields. For instance, women presented higher productivity than men for ENG and SOC book chapters. Previous research has also inquired on gender differences when it comes to scientific production. The novelty of our study comes from the

fact that we've added to this inquiry the effect of grants. Therefore, we not only investigate gender differences, but move to a deeper level of analysis. Female FAPESP awardees also underperform in several fields when compared to male FAPESP awardees. Once again, this isn't the case for every occasion (i.e. women produce more LLA event articles than man), but results do point to higher male productivity. What is noticeable, though, is that both male and female FAPESP awardees do publish more than awardees from other funding agencies and other not awarded individuals. Therefore, the FAPESP research scholarship seems to have a positive effect on the scholarly productivity of all individuals.

The next step of our research is the modeling of our sample. This will allow us to measure the "FAPESP effect". In other words, the precise effect a scholarship from FAPESP, the main state funding agency of Brazil, has over the academic careers of both man and women.

References

Addressi, E., Borgi, M., & Palagi, E. (2012). Is primatology an equal-opportunity discipline?. *PLoS One*, 7(1), e30458.

Bellotti, E., Czerniawska, D., Everett, M. G., & Guadalupi, L. (2022). Gender inequalities in research funding: Unequal network configurations, or unequal network returns? *Social Networks*, 70(December 2021), 138–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2021.12.007>

Lincoln, A. E., Koster, J. B., & Leboy, P. S. (2012). The Matilda Effect in science: Awards and prizes in the US, 1990s and 2000s. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312711435830>

Sugimoto, L. (2018). Mulheres no ensino superior ainda são minoria apenas na docência. *Jornal da Unicamp*.

<<https://www.unicamp.br/unicamp/index.php/ju/noticias/2018/04/11/mulheres-no-ensino-superior-ainda-sao-minoria-apenas-na-docencia>>.